

Part 2 - Literature Update

Section-1: Global Excerpts

Basic Homeopathic Research from Europe – A Report on a Significant Publication

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Editor's Note: The following report is a summary of an article which has been published in 2021 in German Journal of Gastroenterology

Okoubaka shows anti-pathogenic effects against diarrhea pathogens in an in-vitro test system

Acute traveler's diarrhea is one of the most common infectious diseases during long-distance travel. Depending on the destination country, 20-70 % of all travelers are affected. The disease is usually of bacterial origin, with enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), also known as "Montezuma's revenge," accounting for approximately 40 % of cases. *Shigella*, *Salmonella*, and *Campylobacter* are each responsible for 5-10 % of cases.^{1,2}

Okoubaka (*Okoubaka aubrevillei* Pellegr. et Normand)³ is a West African tree which is classified within the sandalwood family. The bark of this tree has a long tradition in West African ethnomedicine, where it is utilized for both protection against poisoning and for treating various other indications, e.g. as a malaria remedy. *Okoubaka* is one of the "younger" homeopathic medicinal products. In the early 1970s, the German doctor Magdalena Kunst brought the bark to Germany and introduced it to homeopathy together with Dr. Willmar Schwabe.⁴ Over the past 40 years, *Okoubaka* has developed into an established homeopathic medicinal product. Meanwhile, *Okoubaka* has a monograph in the German Homeopathic Pharmacopoeia (HAB), and in 1989 a D-monograph with proven indications was published by Commission D (advisory board of the German competent authority, Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices).⁵ Today, *Okoubaka* is firmly established in homeopathy as a remedy related to the gastrointestinal tract.^{6,7} This established role of *Okoubaka* in homeopathy is complemented by newer applications. In his article from 2020, Bagot describes the use of *Okoubaka* in supportive oncological treatment. In view of its application "following an intoxication" and its effect on the digestive system, *Okoubaka* is frequently used in the supportive treatment for chemotherapy-related side effects. In clinical practice, the use of *Okoubaka* was studied in approximately 1000 patients shortly before and during each chemotherapy

session. Its effectiveness in particular in terms of preventing nausea and diarrhea has been confirmed. It has been shown that *Okoubaka*, especially in low dilution, reduces chemotoxic effects and therefore makes a positive contribution to the supportive care in chemotherapy.⁸

Figure 1: Bark of the *Okoubaka* tree. Source: © Susann Buchheim-Schmidt

An *in-vitro* study** examined the anti-pathogenic effects of homeopathic preparations of *Okoubaka aubrevillei* against the two diarrhea pathogens ETEC and *Salmonella enteritidis*. The scientists worked with the hypothesis that the intestinal flora is a self-regulating system that is strengthened by *Okoubaka aubrevillei*.

Methodological Approach

The study was conducted in the so-called SHIME (Simulator of the Human Intestinal Microbial Ecosystem).⁹ This laboratory

**An *in-vitro* study is a scientific investigation conducted outside a living organism. The term "in vitro" comes from Latin and means "in glass." *In-vitro* studies allow the analysis of the effects of substances on cells or microorganisms.

system consists of several compartments representing different sections of the human gastrointestinal tract, allowing the simulation of metabolic processes in the stomach and small intestine as well as the various sections of the large intestine. The investigation was conducted in three steps.

In the **stabilization period**, the stool sample of a healthy donor was introduced into the proximal colon section of the SHIME system. In the present study, this section consisted of 4 parallel "arms." The stabilization period lasted 14 days and was intended to ensure that all 4 arms had the same conditions, corresponding to a well-regulated microbiome (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Experimental setup cited from: Buchheim-Schmidt et al. In vitro evaluation of the antipathogenic activity of *Okoubaka aubrevillei* on the human gastrointestinal tract. Z Gastroenterol 2021; 59: 423–437; with small modifications

This was followed by a one-week treatment with *Okoubaka*, simulating prophylactic intake before a journey. For this

purpose, the stool samples were treated 3 times daily with 5 drops of *Okoubaka* mother tincture, *Okoubaka* 3X (3rd decimal dilution [potency]), or ethanol; the fourth stool sample remained untreated.

In the third step, a bacterial infection was simulated ("**Pathogen Challenge**"). For this purpose, 50 ml samples from the arms treated with ethanol or *Okoubaka* were taken and transferred to small "reactors". Here, 3 drops of *Okoubaka* mother tincture or 3X or ethanol were added to each. The samples were then confronted with the 2 diarrhea-causing bacterial strains ETEC and *Salmonella enteritidis* in 4 different concentrations (Figure 2). The bacterial concentrations were selected to include the minimum infectious doses necessary to cause an infection. After 24 and 48 hours, the germ counts (colony-forming units; CFU) of the pathogens were determined. Additionally, the metabolic activity of the stool sample was determined by the concentration of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs; as acetate, butyrate, and propionate), lactate, ammonium, and branched-chain fatty acids (b-SCFAs) as well as the concentration of the ETEC toxin after 0, 24, and 48 hours (Table 1).

Table 1: Endpoints / Analytical Parameters

Acid / Base consumption	Lactate	SCFA -Acetate -Butyrate -Propionate	Branched SCFA	Ammonium	Anti-pathogenic Activity	Toxins	
X	-	X	-	-	-	-	Stabilization period
X	X	X	X	X	-	-	Treatment period
-	-	X	X	-	X	X	Challenge tests ETEC
-	-	X	X	-	X	-	Challenge tests Salmonella

Cited from: Buchheim-Schmidt et al., 2021, p. 426

Results

The stool samples treated with *Okoubaka* mother tincture and *Okoubaka* 3X reduced the proliferation of ETEC and *Salmonella enteritidis* compared to ethanol in three of the four tested bacterial concentrations (except the highest) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Results of the quantitative colonization of ETEC (using qPCR)

normalized to ethanol control after 24 and 48h of incubation after addition of ETEC in 4 concentrations; 16s RNA copies correspond to CFU (colony forming units). Cited from: Buchheim-Schmidt et al. *In vitro evaluation of the antipathogenic activity of Okoubaka aubrevillei on the human gastrointestinal tract*. *Z Gastroenterol* 2021; 59: 423-437; with small modifications

The best results were achieved at the lowest ETEC concentration. Here, the germ growth in the sample with *Okoubaka* mother tincture was reduced by a factor of 100 (2 log-units^{***}) and in the sample with *Okoubaka* 3X by a factor of 40 (1.6 log-units). This effect was similar after 24 and 48 hours, and the results were statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

The effect decreased with higher bacterial concentrations, and no anti-pathogenic effect could be detected at the highest tested dose.

For *Salmonella enteritidis*, treatment with *Okoubaka* mother tincture led to a reduction in germ growth by a factor of 13 (1.1 log-units) and with *Okoubaka* 3X by a factor of 3 (0.5 log-units), also statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

The analysis of the metabolic activity of the stool samples showed the following: The total concentration of short-chain fatty acids remained unchanged, while the butyrate concentration increased in the first 24 hours ($p < 0.0001$ for ETEC) and the acetate concentration decreased. This effect was stronger for ETEC than for *Salmonella*. The concentration of the ETEC toxin remained unchanged in the *Okoubaka* samples compared to the ethanol control.

^{***}A reduction of two log-units means that germ growth is reduced by 99 percent, while a reduction of one log-unit means a reduction of 90 percent.

Transfer of the results to the in vivo situation and conclusion of the authors

A stool sample pretreated with *Okoubaka* showed an anti-pathogenic effect against two bacterial diarrhea pathogens in vitro by 1-2 log-units (90-99%). If these results are transferred to a living organism, it can be concluded that the preventive intake of *Okoubaka* can help prevent or mitigate the outbreak of traveler's diarrhea. The reduction in germ growth shown in the study gives the body the opportunity to fight existing pathogens. This provides a possible explanation for the successful use of *Okoubaka* for the prevention and treatment of infectious traveler's diarrhea, especially those caused by ETEC: *Okoubaka* strengthens the microbiome.

The altered production of short-chain fatty acids (metabolic activity), particularly the increase in butyrate with a

simultaneous decrease in acetate (so called "cross-feeding"), could additionally enable the organism to alleviate diarrhea, e.g., by reducing the permeability of the intestinal mucosa or closing the tight junctions.^{6,7}

This study is an important contribution to the research on the mode of action of homeopathic medicinal products, especially *Okoubaka*. The results in the gastrointestinal simulator are not comparable to clinical studies in humans. However, the intestinal microbiome simulated here represents a very complex system that could be stimulated and strengthened by the administration of *Okoubaka*. In in-vitro experiments, the placebo effect is irrelevant to the testing process.

These in vitro experiments have considerably increased knowledge of the relatively young remedy *Okoubaka*.

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